

Predicting the Impacts of COVID-19-related Income Changes on Consumption-Based Emissions of UK Neighbourhoods

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Summary

Income is consistently shown to be a good predictor of consumption-based household greenhouse gas emissions. Within a wider research project aiming to understand changes in household emission patterns over time and across UK neighbourhoods, this paper aims to explore the spatial-temporal patterns of the relationship between consumption-based emissions of UK neighbourhoods and income between the years 2007-2017. In light of job losses and income cuts as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, this research allows us to predict how consumption-based emissions may have changed as a result of the pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Carbon footprints, consumption-based emissions, climate mitigation, spatial-temporal analysis

1. Background

It is important for the UK Government to be able to predict and understand greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to meet climate change reduction targets. Yet, despite the UK reporting higher consumption- than production-based GHG emissions, frameworks to measure and mitigate production-based emissions continue to be better understood. While more recent research has begun looking at the UK's consumption-based GHG emissions, neighbourhood level differences in household consumption patterns are not yet well-understood. For instance, while previous research at a Local Authority level highlights that London has some of the highest and lowest consumption-based emissions (Minx et al., 2013), inner-city differences of other cities could not be explored at this geographic level.

GHG footprints are linked to various demographic variables. Higher emissions are often associated with household size, degree of rurality/urbanity, levels of car ownership, and percentage of the population with a higher degree of education, and, most frequently, higher emissions are linked to higher incomes (Vringer and Blok, 1995; Wier et al., 2001; Lenzen et al., 2004; Druckman and Jackson, 2008; Minx et al., 2013). We aim to complement this understanding of income as a reliable predictor of total emissions, by looking at the product-level. In addition, we argue that prediction of emission estimates is important, not just at a national level, but also at a neighbourhood level. This is because, emissions are not equally distributed over space. Cities, for instance, house 55% of the world's population but their consumption-based footprint makes up over 70% of global GHG emissions (C40, 2019). Furthermore, in light of an increased focus of local actors on climate change mitigation, such as the majority of UK local councils and the UK's Local Government Association having declared climate emergencies (LGA, no date), enabling local actors to predict localised emission trends is important to allow for local strategies. The potential impacts of this research are threefold: firstly, differences in emissions between various products and services make it more urgent to reduce consumption of high-emission, non-essential products and services. While this cannot replace a holistic approach that also considers the production-side of emissions, as well as structural factors, it can provide an understanding of how local consumption behaviour can be changed without increasing social inequalities. Secondly,

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a product-level, spatially-detailed approach may allow for an assessment of policy impacts beyond income. For instance, an analysis of Sydney household reveals lower transport energy emissions in some high-income suburban neighbourhoods, as these have increased access to public transport infrastructure (Lenzen et al., 2004). A neighbourhood and product-level assessment of UK household footprints can therefore help monitor effects of sustainability policy on behaviour change and subsequent impacts on emissions. In line with this, this type of research allows for a cross-sectional exploration of spatial differences in emission patterns at fixed income levels and therefore enables a better understanding into how local policy, local infrastructure and other spatial factors can shape behaviour change. Thirdly, evaluating the relationship between income and product-level emissions over time and space allows for a prediction of how consumption-based footprints may change as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and its effect on incomes. This can help us begin to understand how consumption-based emissions may change as a result of the pandemic, in light of geo- and socio-demographic factors.

2. Aim

We aim to generate emission estimates at an MSOA level longitudinally, and to assess the relationship of neighbourhood- and product-level household footprints with income over time. Here this can allow us to predict how consumption-based emissions are impacted by income changes and job losses as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. Method & Data

For data availability reasons we evaluate is done for the years 2007-2017. GHG emissions are estimated using an environmentally-extended input-output analysis, the UKMRIO model, the UK's multi-regional input-output model (see Owen and Barrett, 2020), as well as the Living Costs and Food Survey (LCFS).

We use the UKMRIO to calculate conversion factors: GHG per unit spend (£) by COICOP product. The UKMRIO is a national statistic constructed annually by the University of Leeds following methodology outlined by Tukker et al. (2018) and Edens et al. (2015). Multi-regional input-output databases have been used by environmental economists due to their ability to make the link between the environmental impacts associated with production techniques and the consumers of products. The Leontief input-output model is constructed from observed economic data and shows the interrelationships between industries that consume goods (inputs) from other industries in the process of making their own products (outputs) (Miller et al., 2009). The fundamental Leontief equation, $x=(I-A)^{-1}y$, indicates the inter-industry requirements of each sector to deliver a unit of output to final demand. Since the 1960s, this framework has been extended to account for increases in the pollution associated with industrial production due to a change in final demand.

To disaggregate national emission estimates, we use the LCFS (ONS and Defra, 2020). The LCFS is an openly available annual expenditure survey recording detailed spends from 4,000-6,000 private households across the UK. In addition, expenditure is adjusted using physical use data from the LCFS is used to better estimate consumption of rent and flights.

Using the LCFS, we create regional geodemographic profiles using the information on regions and Output Area Classification available in the LCFS to generate UK wide MSOA expenditure. This expenditure is multiplied by the GHG per unit spend (£) conversion factors to estimate neighbourhood emissions.

4. Future directions

Most immediately, this research allows for an assessment of the relationships between income and emissions over time and space, as well as a prediction of how consumption-based emissions are impacted by income changes and job losses as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. The inclusion of the 2007/08 recession period can further aid our understanding of how economic shock, like the recent lockdowns, job losses, and income changes, can impact emissions. In the future this analysis may also provide some insight into impacts of local transport infrastructure and national and local behaviour change policy and initiatives on consumption behaviours and resulting emissions patterns. Thus, this

research will result in an increased understanding of differences in consumption behaviours between various geo- and socio-demographic groups in UK settlements and how these are affected by access to disposable income and climate change interventions. Finally, understanding changing patterns of emissions and socio-demographic characteristics of neighbourhoods may also provide further insight into how environmental sustainability interventions and policies affect neighbourhoods and their residents differently.

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Biographies

Lena Kilian is a PhD student in the School of Geography, University of Leeds. She is part of the ESRC-funded Centre for Data Analytics and Society. Her research focuses on household greenhouse gas emissions from a consumption perspective. She is particularly interested in the intersections of environmental and social sustainability.

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